

Smart workflows for advanced quality assessment in steel industry: Benefits of I5.0

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Abstract. This paper aims to present the smart workflow proposal in Industry 5.0 context. The adopted example will be the steel industry manufacturing of high-quality coils for the automotive industry, as it is extremely competitive. The proposal will be a self-maintained framework for continuous improvement of artificial intelligence quality models, being enriched by the qualified opinion of operators. Not just the framework but also the general architecture of models will be presented, as well as the way interaction at different frequencies is considered and aside operations related to performance preservation.

Keywords: Industry 5.0, Advanced Quality Control, Smart workflow, Self-maintained framework.

1 Introduction

Modern process plants routinely archive substantial historical data in databases. These databases receive data continuously from numerous online sensors, monitoring hundreds to thousands of variables every few seconds. Effectively utilizing this data is crucial for ensuring the sustained success of industrial processes. These datasets are generally extensive, featuring significant correlations among variables, many of which are collinear, and often lack clear causal relationships [1].

In contemporary times, the advancements brought about by the industry 4.0 paradigm (I4.0) have facilitated the creation of models using latent variable methods like principal component analysis (PCA) and other projection techniques such as projection to latent structures (PLS), among others[2].

Artificial Intelligence (AI) based models, and particularly Deep Learning (DL) have shown great potential in the field of quality control, including in the Hot Dip Galvanizing (HDG) of steel coils [3]. These models can be used to automatically detect defects and other quality issues in the coils, which can help to improve the overall quality of the final product and reduce waste. By analyzing large amounts of data, these models can identify patterns and trends that are indicative of quality issues and use this information to make accurate predictions about the quality of new coils. In addition, deep learning models can be trained to recognize a wide range of defects and quality issues, including those that may be difficult to detect using traditional methods [4].

One of the key advantages of using deep learning models for quality control in HDG is their ability to learn and improve over time. This can help to improve the overall accuracy and efficiency of the quality control process [5].

This type of problems are key aspects of the Industry 5.0 applications, because classification cannot rely on strict figures or rules, but requires some interpretation from the human operators, due their intrinsic knowledge related to usability of the product in upcoming processes, and also because of previous claims from customers [6].

Therefore, although in most of the cases AI based models have been applied to work with 2D dataset (images), it is relevant to determine the industrial applicability to series of 1D data as product descriptions to be classified. In this way there are several research questions to be addressed,

RQ1: Are Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) suitable to promote reliable classification technique when the input are series on 1-D measures?

RQ2: Is it possible to propose an operating framework enabling the self-detection for retraining, without data-scientist participation?

Hereinafter the paper will be structured as follows. First, a literature review section is presented. The next section looks to introduce details about the rationale of the use case of interest, including data preprocessing. The next section will present the CNN architecture and the results found. The next Section will introduce the operative framework based on workflows, and finally the last section will discuss the conclusions.

2 State of the Art

The topics being addressed are linked to Industry 5.0, although they are evolving from Industry 4.0 core concepts, such as using AI based models to classify products[4, 7, 8].

In quality control applications, the necessity of learning from actual data exists, but it comes with limitations. This is due to the business logic, which tends to generate a higher ratio of good products compared to damaged ones. This poses a challenge to the learning process, as it is a well-known issue associated with imbalanced datasets[5, 9, 10].

Artificial intelligence technologies play a pivotal role in intelligent fault diagnosis by automating and imbuing intelligence into the diagnostic process [11]. In recent times, deep neural networks, including deep auto-encoders [12], deep convolutional neural networks [13], and various other deep networks [14] and significantly advancing the field. Traditional algorithms were originally developed to extract knowledge from

static datasets. However, in contrast, modern data sources produce information that is characterized by both its volume and velocity, which is particularly significant in industrial settings. Unlike learning from static data, the challenge here lies in the need to adapt to the dynamic nature of the data, where concepts are not constant and can change over time. This phenomenon is often referred to as "concept drift" [15], and when not effectively managed, it can lead to a deterioration in the performance of the classifier, as knowledge acquired about previous concepts may no longer be applicable to recent instances [16].

Resampling algorithms can be classified into two categories: blind and informed. Blind approaches lack the utilization of information about minority class properties to a significant extent. Although blind methods can be efficiently integrated into ensembles due to their low computational cost, they often exhibit suboptimal performance when used independently [16]. Most resampling methods for data streams are informed and based on a very popular SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) or Incremental Oversampling for Data Streams (IOSDS), where different implementations have been proposed [17–22].

Another important consideration in the integration of artificial intelligence into manufacturing is the transformation of jobs and the emergence of opportunities for human-machine collaboration, leveraging the complementary capabilities of both. One approach to facilitate such collaboration is through the Active Learning paradigm [23]. This approach acknowledges that an artificial intelligence model can be enhanced by thoughtfully selecting a small number of data instances that align with a specific learning objective. Hence, applied research is centered on devising methods to structure solutions for use cases. This involves incorporating a human-in-the-loop approach, where artificial intelligence models leverage human expertise to make decisions and receive valuable input [24]. This collaborative process is instrumental in refining and improving the models over time and it is the spirit of the solution carried out here, by leveraging the different frequencies of operation from the automatic classification system and the feedback from the human operators as well as their diversity.

Lastly, and certainly of significant importance, another well-documented challenge is the requirement for continuous retraining. Despite the extensive use of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) in systems like self-driving cars, there has been limited progress in automating the support for functional safety analysis in DNN-based systems. Particularly, identifying the root causes of errors, which is essential for both risk analysis and DNN retraining, remains an unsolved challenge [25].

3 Application Case

The motivation of the selected use case is to explore how to elaborate classification algorithm on a series of 1-D data that require to be considered together for making a suggestion about the quality of the product. The industrial use case considered is the one related to assess the thickness of coated zinc layers protecting hot dip galvanized steel coils to be used in automotive industry as well as in other industries [1, 26–29].

To illustrate the process and the collected information the **Fig. 1**, presents the latest part of the hot dip galvanizing (HDG) process for a coil, where the thickness measurement is carried out and the information collected from each of the nine X-ray gauges measuring the zinc thickness of coating per face of the coil. The ultimate quality of galvanized steel strip is contingent upon several factors, including the material surface, zinc adhesion, and the uniformity of coating weight. While the first two parameters are influenced by proper substrate cleaning and strip temperature control, the assessment of the third parameter, coating weight, often occurs too late in the process for timely corrections. In practice, many producers verify the hot dip zinc coating weight after the coil has exited the mill. If the results are deemed unsatisfactory at this stage, the entire coil must be downgraded or scrapped, leading to delays, wastage of raw materials, and increased expenses [30].

Fig. 1. Left: General schema of the thickness measurement of Zn coated coils [31]. Right: Longitudinal expression of the zinc coating thickness per face and with the customer requirement marked in yellow.

In HDG lines, ensuring automatic coating weight control is crucial for achieving uniform production with minimized zinc consumption. The key to obtaining precise measurements of the zinc coating weight on steel strips lies in conducting these measurements during the production process, rather than after. X-ray fluorescence (XRF) technology emerges as an excellent solution to achieve the required precision without incurring costly and time-consuming delays in production. Online metal coating weight gauges, employing XRF technology, have demonstrated success in providing non-contact coating weight measurements that can be configured for nearly every type of metal-coated product [32]. This is particularly advantageous for obtaining accurate total zinc coating weight measurements on challenging-to-measure surfaces, such as galvalneal-coated sheets.

Continuous thickness measurement in the high-speed HDG line is segmented into 10-meter tiles, where both average and standard deviation are taken into consideration. Consequently, pertinent information per coil face comprises a variable-length tuple of values. The size of these tuples is contingent on the number of XRF gauges in use, which, in our application, amounts to nine. Additionally, we have adopted the saliency

approach [33, 34], wherein the thickness information is mapped based on the customer-defined range of thickness. In this scenario, when the current value falls within the range, a 0 value is assigned. If the current value is below the lower threshold, a negative value is coded to represent the difference. Conversely, if the current value exceeds the maximum threshold, a positive value is coded to denote the difference.

To be able to exploit the tensorial properties of the DNN, global determination of maximum and minimum saliency values, as well as the maximum number of tiles across the whole coil datasets are determined, enabling to normalize both the geometry number of virtual tiles and their values, falling in (-1,1) range for the variation of saliency. A sample overview of the customized data can be seen in **Fig. 2**.

```
GlblFrm
```

```
{'NormMn': -279.38157, 'NormMx': 507.54791, 'MaxTiles': 264}
```

```
nclmaps2[lcoils[0]][1234]['nzne']
```

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
0	0.0	0.0	-0.018095	0.000000	0.000000	-0.090299	-0.111732	-0.137263	-0.153288
1	0.0	0.0	-0.018095	-0.000327	-0.001679	-0.094247	-0.120618	-0.150700	-0.170367
2	0.0	0.0	-0.018095	-0.000655	-0.003358	-0.098194	-0.129503	-0.164137	-0.187447
3	0.0	0.0	-0.018095	-0.000982	-0.005037	-0.102142	-0.138388	-0.177574	-0.204527
4	0.0	0.0	-0.018095	-0.001310	-0.006716	-0.106089	-0.147274	-0.191010	-0.221607
...
259	0.0	0.0	0.000000	0.000000	0.003587	0.000000	0.000000	-0.042661	-0.101621
260	0.0	0.0	0.000000	0.000000	0.003587	0.000000	0.000000	-0.042661	-0.101621
261	0.0	0.0	0.000000	0.000000	0.003587	0.000000	0.000000	-0.042661	-0.101621
262	0.0	0.0	0.000000	0.000000	0.003587	0.000000	0.000000	-0.042661	-0.101621
263	0.0	0.0	0.000000	0.000000	0.003587	0.000000	0.000000	-0.042661	-0.101621

264 rows × 9 columns

Fig. 2. Overview for a coil's top face involving the 264 virtual tiles (rows) and X-ray gauges (columns) properly normalized. The global values are retained in GlblFrm structure to facilitate to recover the real meaning of the values.

With this information properly elaborated, the modelling step can be addressed.

4 Model Architecture

To measure the quality of the models in a fair and unbiased way, we separate a random set of coils with leveraged participation of each class to be kept out of the modelling phase. In our application 30 coils per class were frozen to measure independent quality performance over them.

With the remaining dataset a classical segmentation between training, validation and test subsets were created, by the common 70%,20%, 10% approach, where data augmentation on the minor class has been considered for training subset. The data augmentation implemented followed the auto-augment algorithm [35]. Enabling transformations that align with the manufacturing process, the data augmentation factory has implemented horizontal and vertical mirroring across the middle axis. Additionally, incremental x-shift, with continuous feeding of the information extracted, has been incorporated to enhance the dataset.

The model architecture was prototyped according to the schema described in **Table 1**. The model involves 1148068 trainable parameters out of 1148196 total ones.

Table 1. CNN model architecture.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param#
conv1d_28 (Conv1D)	multiple	11552
batch_normalization_14 (BatchNormalization)	multiple	128
conv1d_29 (Conv1D)	multiple	20512
batch_normalization_15 (BatchNormalization)	multiple	128
spatial_dropout1d_14 (SpatialDropout1D)	multiple	0
conv1d_30 (Conv1D)	multiple	6176
average_pooling1d_7 (AveragePooling1D)	multiple	0
conv1d_31 (Conv1D)	multiple	6176
conv1d_32 (Conv1D)	multiple	6176
spatial_dropout1d_15 (SpatialDropout1D)	multiple	0
flatten_7 (Flatten)	multiple	0
dense_28 (Dense)	multiple	1089576
dropout_21 (Dropout)	multiple	0
dense_29 (Dense)	multiple	43956
dropout_22 (Dropout)	multiple	0
dense_30 (Dense)	multiple	11026
dropout_23 (Dropout)	multiple	0
dense_31 (Dense)	multiple	150

The classification performance over the test subset is presented in **Table 2**, where accuracy F1-Score is 0.79 for the total of 63 samples.

Table 2. CNN model performance.

Label	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
OK	0.95	0.79	0.86	52
NoK	0.45	0.82	0.58	11

When considering the dataset extracted for measuring the quality, results are presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3. CNN model performance.

Label	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
OK	0.83	0.83	0.83	30
NoK	0.83	0.83	0.83	30

When the confusion matrix is considered, the results are presented in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Confusion matrix for the CNN classifier.

Predicted \ Real	OK	NoK
OK	25	5
NoK	5	25

5 Proposed Framework

Once the CNN model was proved as a proper solution for scoring coils when human adapted criteria are enforced, although still depending on training process and on the limited data sample available, it is required to deploy it in an unattended configuration able to provide the opinion in a robust way, but even more importantly, to decide when one model becomes biased, and retraining is needed.

Fig. 3. Framework integrating design and implementation with feedback as proposed in this research.

As the key aspect is the automatic reaction to the events requesting a coil assessment, one framework relying on the LASFA+ paradigm[36] is proposed in this paper, and it

considers the automatic retraining process as well. Its general overview is presented in **Fig. 3**.

The framework is based on the idea of a design phase carried out in back-office, before promoting the implementation of the system. Later on the implementation phase includes the ensemble construction of selected models and its application for prediction, but also the integration of the decisions made by the operators as a way to measure the performance of the individual models and their need for retraining.

The practical implementation of such a framework is carried out by using NiFi™ technology [37], as it fits well with modern microservice oriented computing platforms orchestrated by Kubernetes [38] (see **Fig. 4**).

Fig. 4. Implementation in NiFi™ data workflow of the two main workflows (Coil Assessment and Model retraining).

6 Conclusions

The paper introduces a framework for the automated operation of deep learning based classification including the human perspectives and criteria, with automatic retraining based on asynchronous performance assessment because of the smart implementation of data workflows. The proposal comes after verifying that the proposed Deep Learning solution is feasible and fits with the requirements, in complete agreement with the promoted framework. Therefore, it was possible to successfully answer the two research questions formulated.

The inherent advantage of the suggested workflow solution lies in its complete automation achieved through triggers implemented via updates on the PostgreSQL™ tables database. Furthermore, scalability is ensured through the utilization of a microservices solution.

However, certain limitations have been acknowledged. For instance, the integration of deep transfer learning technologies into the ensemble solution is constrained by the necessity for backend processes. Similarly, there is a need to explore contrastive learning to evaluate the likelihood of each coil.

Another aspect to be developed further is the UI for providing a visual tool helping to understand the average life of each model as per type as well as the population of models in the operating ensemble, in such a way that the model explainability aspect increases and makes the data scientists aware of the global evolution of the classification system through time in an easy way.

The last aspect to be examined pertains to the performance of the involved services during specific time periods, particularly when correlated with the demand for coil assessments and requested feedback.

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References

1. Ordieres Meré JB, González Marcos A, González JA, Lobato Rubio V (2004) Estimation of mechanical properties of steel strip in hot dip galvanising lines. *Ironmaking & steelmaking* 31:43–50
2. Çnar ZM, Abdussalam Nuhu A, Zeeshan Q, et al (2020) Machine learning in predictive maintenance towards sustainable smart manufacturing in industry 4.0. *Sustainability* 12:8211
3. Colla V, Cateni S, Maddaloni A, Vignali A (2020) A Modular Machine-Learning-Based Approach to Improve Tensile Properties Uniformity Along Hot Dip Galvanized Steel Strips for Automotive Applications. *Metals* 2020, Vol 10, Page 923 10:923. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MET10070923>
4. Perez H, Tah JHM, Mosavi A (2019) Deep Learning for Detecting Building Defects Using Convolutional Neural Networks. *Sensors* 2019, Vol 19, Page 3556 19:3556. <https://doi.org/10.3390/S19163556>
5. Al-Darraji S, Honi DG, Fallucchi F, et al (2021) Employee Attrition Prediction Using Deep Neural Networks. *Computers* 2021, Vol 10, Page 141 10:141. <https://doi.org/10.3390/COMPUTERS10110141>
6. Bounouar M, Bearee R, Siadat A, Benchekroun TH (2022) On the role of human operators in the design process of cobotic systems. *Cognition, Technology and Work* 24:57–73. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10111-021-00691-Y/FIGURES/10>

7. Wang S, Xia X, Ye L, Yang B (2021) Automatic Detection and Classification of Steel Surface Defect Using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks. *Metals* 2021, Vol 11, Page 388 11:388. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MET11030388>
8. Chakraborty A, Mondal A, Agnihotri S, et al (2016) Investigation of a surface defect and its elimination in automotive grade galvanized steels. *Eng Fail Anal* 66:455–467
9. Johnson JM, Khoshgoftaar TM (2019) Survey on deep learning with class imbalance. *J Big Data* 6:1–54. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40537-019-0192-5/TABLES/13>
10. Gong B, Ordieres-Meré J (2016) Prediction of daily maximum ozone threshold exceedances by preprocessing and ensemble artificial intelligence techniques: Case study of Hong Kong. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 84:290–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVSOFT.2016.06.020>
11. Pan J, Zi Y, Chen J, et al (2018) LiftingNet: A Novel Deep Learning Network with Layerwise Feature Learning from Noisy Mechanical Data for Fault Classification. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 65:4973–4982. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2017.2767540>
12. Jiang W, Zhou J, Liu H, Shan Y (2019) A multi-step progressive fault diagnosis method for rolling element bearing based on energy entropy theory and hybrid ensemble auto-encoder. *ISA Trans* 87:235–250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ISATRA.2018.11.044>
13. Zhang K, Chen J, Zhang T, Zhou Z (2020) A Compact Convolutional Neural Network Augmented with Multiscale Feature Extraction of Acquired Monitoring Data for Mechanical Intelligent Fault Diagnosis. *J Manuf Syst* 55:273–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JMSY.2020.04.016>
14. Pan T, Chen J, Pan J, Zhou Z (2020) A Deep Learning Network via Shunt-Wound Restricted Boltzmann Machines Using Raw Data for Fault Detection. *IEEE Trans Instrum Meas* 69:4852–4862. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2019.2953436>
15. Khamassi I, Sayed-Mouchaweh M, Hammami M, Ghédira K (2018) Discussion and review on evolving data streams and concept drift adapting. *Evolving Systems* 9:1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12530-016-9168-2/FIGURES/16>
16. Aguiar G, Krawczyk B, Cano A (2023) A survey on learning from imbalanced data streams: taxonomy, challenges, empirical study, and reproducible experimental framework. *Mach Learn* 1–79. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10994-023-06353-6/FIGURES/3>
17. Cubuk ED, Zoph B, Mane D, et al (2018) Autoaugment: Learning augmentation policies from data. arXiv preprint arXiv:180509501
18. Dwivedi R (2020) How Data Augmentation Impacts Performance Of Image Classification. In: analyticsindiamag.com. <https://analyticsindiamag.com/image-data-augmentation-impacts-performance-of-image-classification-with-codes/>. Accessed 16 Mar 2023
19. Dilmegani C (2021) Top Data Augmentation Techniques: Ultimate Guide for 2023. In: research.aimultiple.com. <https://research.aimultiple.com/data-augmentation-techniques/>. Accessed 16 Mar 2023

20. Cubuk ED, Zoph B, Shlens J, Le Q V (2020) Randaugment: Practical automated data augmentation with a reduced search space. In: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition workshops. pp 702–703
21. Mikołajczyk A, Grochowski M (2018) Data augmentation for improving deep learning in image classification problem. In: 2018 International Interdisciplinary PhD Workshop (IIPhDW). pp 117–122
22. Ratner AJ, Ehrenberg H, Hussain Z, et al (2017) Learning to compose domain-specific transformations for data augmentation. *Adv Neural Inf Process Syst* 30:
23. Qu T, Guan S, Feng YT, et al (2023) Deep active learning for constitutive modelling of granular materials: From representative volume elements to implicit finite element modelling. *Int J Plast* 164:103576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJPLAS.2023.103576>
24. Kumar P, Gupta A (2020) Active Learning Query Strategies for Classification, Regression, and Clustering: A Survey. *J Comput Sci Technol* 35:913–945. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11390-020-9487-4/METRICS>
25. Attaoui M, Fahmy H, Pastore F, Briand L (2023) Black-box Safety Analysis and Retraining of DNNs based on Feature Extraction and Clustering. *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology* 32:79. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3550271>
26. Rose A, Wandera C, Favor E (2021) Parameters Influencing the Hot Dip Galvanizing Processes of Sheet Metal. *American Journal of Materials Synthesis and Processing* 6:1
27. Saravanan P, Srikanth S (2018) Surface defects and their control in hot dip galvanized and galvanized sheets. *International Journal of Advanced Research In Chemical Science (Ijarcs)* 5:11–23
28. González-Marcos A, Ordieres-Meré JB, Pernía-Espinoza AV, Torre-Suárez V (2008) Development of an artificial lock for the skin-pass section in a hot dip galvanising line. *Revista de Metalurgia (Madrid)* 44:
29. Gonzalez-Marcos A, Alba-Elias F, Castejon-Limas M, Ordieres-Mere J (2011) Development of neural network-based models to predict mechanical properties of hot dip galvanized steel coils. *International Journal of Data Mining, Modelling and Management* 3:389–405
30. Verma N, Sharma V, Badar MA, et al (2022) Optimization of Zinc Coating Thickness by Unreplicated Factorial Design of Experiments in Hot-Dip Galvanization Process. *International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing* 23:1173–1182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12541-022-00695-2/FIGURES/6>
31. Measuring Zinc Coating Weight on Galvanized Steel. <https://www.thermofisher.com/blog/metals/unique-sensor-design-accurately-measures-zinc-coating-weight-on-galvanized-steel/>. Accessed 20 Nov 2023
32. Jones A, Uggalla L, Li K, et al (2021) Continuous In-Line Chromium Coating Thickness Measurement Methodologies: An Investigation of Current and

- Potential Technology. *Sensors* 2021, Vol 21, Page 3340 21:3340. <https://doi.org/10.3390/S21103340>
33. Guan S (2015) Strip Steel Defect Detection Based on Saliency Map Construction Using Gaussian Pyramid Decomposition. *ISIJ International* 55:1950–1955. <https://doi.org/10.2355/isijinternational.ISIJINT-2015-041>
 34. Abdelaziz M, Zhang Z (2021) Few-shot learning with saliency maps as additional visual information. *Multimed Tools Appl* 80:10491–10508
 35. An J, Jang S, Kwon J, et al (2022) Saliency guided data augmentation strategy for maximally utilizing an object’s visual information. *PLoS One* 17:e0274767
 36. Sun S, Zheng X, Villalba-Díez J, Ordieres-Meré J (2020) Data Handling in Industry 4.0: Interoperability Based on Distributed Ledger Technology. *Sensors* 20:3046. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20113046>
 37. Liu J, Braun E, Döpmeier C, et al (2018) A Generic and Highly Scalable Framework for the Automation and Execution of Scientific Data Processing and Simulation Workflows. In: 2018 IEEE International Conference on Software Architecture (ICSA). pp 145–14510
 38. Taherizadeh S, Grobelnik M (2020) Key influencing factors of the Kubernetes auto-scaler for computing-intensive microservice-native cloud-based applications. *Advances in Engineering Software* 140:102734